

Scenario 2: Extensive use of technology, worsening the quality of education and with teachers poorly prepared for the adoption of these technologies

In 2038, the socioeconomic reality in Brazil is almost dystopian. The last pandemic, quelled five years ago, with its four years of severe presence, requiring various restrictive measures, with more than 500,000 deaths, affirmed the causal conditions of the deterioration of the reality above. This reality is a direct result of the various shifts in power between populist left and right-wing governments, in a degrading process bringing as a common trait blind and ideological statism, the increase in state bureaucracy, conservatism in customs, albeit with the presence of non-aligned ghettos to dominant values, the strong presence of Christian religious fundamentalism, and the exacerbation of executive power over the other constituent powers of the Republic. The population, now around 230 million people, balanced between sexes, has aged. The birth rate, close to one, and the flight of the young, middle, and upper-class population to Asian or African countries affirm this aging picture (the average age of the economically active population has exceeded forty-five years). The young population from the lower classes, primarily black, continues to suffer, as they have for the past 150 years, from the exterminating action of repressive governments. The pension crisis worsens, with no more security of access to essential benefits, including retirement.

The Brazilian economy is sentenced to the condition of a supplier of agricultural commodities resulting from a predatory and marginalized agribusiness due to harmful practices. These businesses are highly automated, with little contribution to employment, making urban centers densely populated facing the uninhabited countryside. In the energy economy, the lack of research has minimized Brazilian opportunities for green and clean energy. With insignificant positive results, Brazil now sells energy from degraded hydroelectric plants of low efficiency and buys gas and oil supplements from Latin American countries. The meager industrial park adds little to the national GDP and the number of jobs. Jobs are heavily concentrated in the service sector.

In 2038, Brazilian society presents a predominantly neoconservative profile, with strong religious contamination in all areas of the state and reigning physiological and utilitarian interpersonal relationships. The arts and their conveying structures, although presenting few pockets of stimulating and progressive expressions, are widely bureaucratized, uncreative, and conservative, vectored through financing and specific repressive legislation by the will of a conservative State, presenting mediocre levels of contribution to the field of creative economy. In addition, aspects such as technological dependence, the commodification of education, the impact on mental health, ethical and privacy issues related to Artificial Intelligence (AI), and the precariousness of teaching work are emerging concerns that must be considered.

In education, regulatory bodies, strongly subjected to the desires of neoliberal and religious segments, legislate towards deepening deregulation of formations and banalization of content, favoring all teaching modalities that use digital robots, AI, and mobile technologies to maximize profit by replacing professors. However, it is important to recognize that the rapid adoption of technologies does not necessarily lead to a deterioration in the quality of education. Appropriate educational policies can mitigate this risk; if well implemented, technology can benefit education. Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) have a purely commercial relationship with students to quickly sell diplomas – which maintain some presence to occupy public positions, ensuring some commercial attractiveness. The contingent of education professionals in the classroom is 80% smaller compared to 2022. Professors act as monitors and feeders of AI and other online teaching structures, being trained for such. However, the inadequate preparation of professors to deal with new technologies is a recurring concern. It is essential to ensure adequate training for professors to integrate technologies into teaching effectively. Such AI dominates the online environment predominantly, except for courses in the wealth area, which are very expensive, which combine in a hybrid manner the robots, IA, and mobile applications with professors.

Public higher education is condemned to obsolescence due to contamination by ideological combats, being heavily disorganized, and being abandoned by the government. Although the large installed network, public higher education encompasses only about 20% of the university population. The lack of public tenders for teaching presents a low contingent of aged, outdated,

and bureaucratized teachers. With the substitute presence of robots/IA/mobile, these replacements are precarious due to lack of funding and administrative inefficiency. The historically inefficient professor training for higher education, previously partially supported by Master's and Doctorate courses, now no longer exists. Also, interest in the profession, with low social recognition and low remuneration, is practically nonexistent. Despite the challenges, there is recognition of the positive potential of technology in education. It is essential to implement effective educational policies to maximize the potential benefits of technology.

The public higher education sector has long ceased to be a reference for quality for students and the job market for professionals with higher education. The influence of economic groups on education and social and access inequalities are seen as aggravating factors, requiring attention in developing future educational strategies.

Physically, private HEIs centralize structures in a few headquarters, branching out their operations nationally through poles – small and functional facilities with complementary and bureaucratic functions – with no physical library. Using digital communication networks, these digital and virtual laboratories disseminate their classes throughout the Brazilian territory, coming from specific and few disseminator centers. Exceptions to the formations in affluent areas, which tend to be prohibitively expensive and elitist, are found in the specific professional cycles offered at various installations affiliated with HEIs within large private wealth groups. These programs integrate cutting-edge technologies such as robotics, artificial intelligence (AI), and mobile platforms into their foundational curricula. In the professional cycle, the presence of the human professor and face-to-face activity significantly appears. The content of various courses is reduced to what the owners of HEIs and government bureaucrats consider “a sufficient minimum.” Added to the insignificant evaluative processes and instruments, they create an extremely precarious training environment, opening up space for free courses. These are heavily occupied by the same groups that operate private higher education, presenting the possibility of effective certified training in specific and necessary skills for the job market. Thus, the bureaucratic character of the diploma is still important for access to public positions (certainly, this access condition is the touchstone for the sustenance of the educational segment until now). For a more holistic and

inclusive approach to adopting technologies in higher education, ensuring equity in access to technologies, maintaining the quality of education, and developing effective public and institutional policies is crucial.

Technical education at the high school level suffers from other ailments, some similar to those mentioned above. Occupied symmetrically by public and private administration, it is a victim of the deterioration of Basic Education. The stratum of the population that attends elementary school in schools with a considerable standard of quality, high class historically, is not interested in technical training at the high school level. Thus, the economic and strategic potential of this formative level is eroded by the low quality of this training, undoubtedly because it is a continuation of a bad previous training-elementary education for those interested in this formative modality, as well as by the lack of interest of the job market for the graduates. Thus, investments in this segment decrease.

Returning to higher education, several courses that did not exist ten years ago proliferate; others, traditional, survive only in public education. The newly proposed courses are attempts to cover demands from the job market, which they find difficult due to the obsolescence and superficiality of the content taught in them.

Brazilian private higher education, in 2038, survives bureaucratically as a diploma issuer fueled by public benefits and enrolled in several government financing programs for low-income students. It is at a critical moment of severe threats and few business opportunities.